

A BETTER UNDERSTANDING OF HUMAN RIGHTS FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF SEMIOTICS

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ABSTRACT: A Better Understanding of Human Rights from the Perspective of Semiotics.

The current society is under the empire of human rights. In the rhetoric of this field, there are ubiquitous terms such as *equality*, *freedom*, *diversity*, concepts that have begun to be the subject of a relatively recent discipline: semiotics or, also called, semiology. Through this paper we try to show a series of results of the semiotic analyzes carried out in the sphere of human rights. The specificity of the studies in the field consists in researching the existing relationships between the signified and the signifier, the process of assigning meanings to the mentioned theme. The researchers' concerns focused on several topics related to human rights: legal language, corporate world in relation to human rights, the influence of culture in the understanding of human rights and so on. The research has brought to light the fact that regarding the terms representing human rights used in the legal system and those used in society, there is an obvious discrepancy. Also, in order to decode some visual messages, a more in-depth knowledge is needed than that offered by the existing consensus at the level of society, by which it is clearly known that certain objects can only have one meaning or another. Sometimes the decryption code of the message, is not obvious.

Keywords: *concept, meaning, equality, language, image*

Conceptual approaches in the field of semiotics

Communication between people involves the transmission of information in relation to the reality in which they live. Also, it is based on representations

of things, objects, beings, etc. with which we come into contact or whose existence we are aware of. A number of fields of study focus on communication, on language, on representations and on how information can be transmitted from one individual to another, so that communication is effective. How is communication possible, even when two interlocutors don't speak the same language? How does the brain manage to decode the message sent by others? Apart from linguistics, pragmatics, the philosophy of language, onomastics, anthropology, sociology, communication theories - semiotics occupies a special position among the disciplines concerned with answering such questions. While for the father of semiotics, Ferdinand de Saussure, semiology (also called by some researchers in the field as semiotics) is "a science that studies the life of signs within society"¹ (Saussure, 2011:16) , or "a science of forms, since it studies significations apart from their contents"² for Roland Barthes, other researchers consider that semiotics is not necessary a discipline, but "the study of the innate capacity of human beings to produce and understand signs of all kinds (from those belonging to simple physiological signaling systems to those which reveal a highly complex symbolic structure)"³ (Sebeok, 1994:xii), "a method of approach dominated by the perspective of the sign"⁴ (Golopenția, 2019:21).

Ferdinand de Saussure offers a dyadic model of the sign. According to this Swedish theorist, the sign is composed by the *signifier* (how the sign appears, its form) and the *signified* (the concept to which it refers). Talking about significations, he will speak of *linguistics signs*. Saussure defines the linguistic sign as a link between a concept (the signified) and a sound pattern/sound-image⁵ (the signifier). Contrary to appearances, the sound pattern does not consist of a sound, but it is "the hearer's psychological impression of a sound, as given to him by the evidence of his senses"⁶/"the

1 Saussure, Ferdinand, *Course in General Linguistics*, Columbia University Press, New York, Chichester, West Sussex, 2011, p.16.

2 Barthes, Roland, *Mythologies*, The Noonday Press – New York, 1991, p.110.

3 Sebeok, A. Thomas, *An Introduction to Semiotics*, University of Toronto Press Incorporated, Toronto, 1994, p. xii.

4 Golopenția, Sanda, *Studii de semiotică (Semiotic Studies)*, Editura Academiei Române, București, 2019, p. 21.

5 The terms are translated differently in English, but they refer to the same thing. Thus, in the original quote from Daniel Chandler's book (2007), we find the expression 'sound pattern', while in the translation of Saussure's work by Wade Baskin (2011), the term 'sound-image' is used instead.

6 Chandler, Daniel, *Semiotics: the Basics*, second edition, Routledge Taylor & Francis Group, London and New York, 2007, p. 14.

psychological imprint of the sound, the impression that it makes on our senses”⁷. While the concept (the signified) is more abstract, the sound pattern/sound-image (the signifier is sensory). The characteristics of the linguistic sign are its arbitrary nature and the linear nature of the signifier (which is not always obvious). The first characteristic consists in the fact that the connection between the signifier and the signified is arbitrary. The concept is not linked in any way to the succession of sounds found in the word which acts as the signifier. As for the linear nature of the signifier, due to its auditory nature “is unfolded solely in time from which it gets the following characteristics: (a) it represents a span, and (b) the span is measurable in a single dimension: it is a line”⁸. Although the visual signifiers can offer simultaneous groupings in several dimensions, the auditory signifiers only have the dimension of time (duration). Their elements being presented in succession, they will form a chain or a line.

In present the signifier is interpreted as the material or physical form of the sign, which can be perceived through our senses (touch, hearing, sight etc.). The connection between the signifier and the signified is called by Saussure – “signification”.

Peirce’s sign theory is based on the assumption that the human universe is eminently symbolic, full of signs:

“Whenever we think, we have a feeling, an image, a concept, or another representation present in our consciousness, which serves as a sign. (...) Therefore, when we think, we ourselves, as we are at that moment, appear as a sign. Now, a sign has, as such, three references: first, it is a sign in relation to some thought, which interprets it; secondly, it is a sign for some object, with which it is equivalent in that thought; thirdly, it is a sign in some respect or quality that puts it in relation to its object. Let’s ask ourselves which are the three correlates to which a thought-sign refers.”⁹

Man cannot think without signs, because the only thought that can be recognized is in signs. The thought-sign represents the object that has real existence (that we think about). He is the thought itself. Peirce identifies three elements specific to thinking: the representative function, which

7 Saussure, Ferdinand, *op. cit.*, p. 66.

8 *Ibidem*, p. 70.

9 Peirce, S. Charles, *Semnificație și acțiune (Semnification and Action)*, București, Editura Humanitas, 1990, p. 82.

makes thinking a representation, then the denotative application, which makes the connection between two thoughts (puts them in relation to one another), and, thirdly, the material quality of the thought (as is this felt, a fact that confers its quality). His model is triadic in nature, different from Saussure's "self-contained dyad" and consisting on the following elements:

1. The *representamen*: the form the sign takes, which is not necessarily material, in the field of semiotics it is also used under the name of "sign vehicle";
2. An *interpretant*: not to be confused with an interpreter, it is about the sense made by the sign – "creates in the mind of the person an equivalent sign or (...) a more developed sign";
3. An *object*: a *referent* ("The sign stands for (...) its object. It stands for that object, not in all respects, but in reference to a sort of idea, which I have sometimes called the ground of the representamen.")¹⁰.

The interaction between the three elements is called *semeiosis*. The process of *semeiosis* is the process of decoding a sign and it was explained by analogy with a box with a label on it, the label suggesting that it contains something inside and after reading the label we find out what it contains. The first thing that is noticed is the *representamen* – the box and the label; then comes the realisation that something is in the box (*the object*). The realization and the knowledge of what the box contains is provided by *the interpretant*. The process of decoding the sign is symbolized in this example by 'reading the label'.

"The important point to be aware of here is that the object of a sign is always hidden. We cannot actually open the box and inspect it directly. The reason for this is simple: if the object could be known directly, there would be no need of a sign to represent it. We only know about the object from noticing the label and the box and then 'reading the label' and forming a mental picture of the object in our mind. Therefore the hidden object of a sign is only brought to realization through the interaction of the *representamen*, the object and the *interpretant*."¹¹

As Daniel Chandler observes, there are similarities between Saussure's theory and Peirce's in terms of the elements they work with: Peirce's *representamen* being similar to Saussure's signifier.

10 *Ibidem*, p. 269.

11 Peirce, S. Charles *apud* Chandler, Daniel, *Semiotics: the Basics*, second edition, Routledge Taylor & Francis Group, London and New York, 2007, p. 31.

The word sign can denote a perceptible object, an imaginable one or even unimaginable to a certain extent (here the theorist gives the example of the word *fast*, which is a sign, it is not imaginable because it can only be put on paper or pronounced in a court of its own; although it is the same written or spoken word, it is a different word depending on what it refers to)¹².

Peirce also offered a few categorizations of signs. The most well-known classification was developed taking into account the relationships between the representamen and its interpretant or its object. The signs have three modes:

1. *Symbolic* – in which the signifier does not resemble the signified, being fundamentally arbitrary, or purely conventional – “this relationship must be agreed upon and learned”¹³, established by mutual agreement of the people (example: the language, the numbers);
2. *Icon* – in which the signifier is perceived as replicating or resembling the signified (in all human senses); they both have some characteristics in common (example: a drawing, a portrait, a sculpture, onomatopoeia, sound effects, gestures that imitate certain attributes of some people or things etc.)
3. *Index* – in which the signifier is directly connected in some way to the signified (the connection can be physically or causally). The link between them can be observed, perceived through our senses, or inferred (example: ‘natural signs’ – smells, thunder, smoke, echoes; medical symptoms associated with different diseases; recordings; ‘signals’ – they can be conventional or non-conventional: the raid sirens, the phone ringing, onomatopoeia, personal ‘trademarks’ – writing, verbal tics etc.).

Roland Barthes starts from the idea of myth to lay the foundations of his theory. For him the myth is “a kind of speech”, “a system of communication that it is a message”, not “an object, a concept or an idea, it is a mode of signification, a form”¹⁴. Every real object can become a myth provided that the man, the society talks about it, appropriates it, charging it with a social use, with a meaning, that is significance. Therefore the myth is

12 Peirce, S. Charles, *op. cit.*, p. 270.

13 Chandler, Daniel, *op. cit.*, p. 36.

14 Barthes, Roland, *op. cit.*, p. 107.

born when the reality is converted into speech. Being a message, mythical speech can have a wide variety of supports, not only oral. It can be carried by written discourse, photography, art representations, publicity etc. The real object gets to have a particular image, loaded with its own signification. In his essays Barthes explains that in semiology there are three important terms with which this science theorizes: the signifier, the signified and the relation between them – the sign. The sign is “the associative total of the first two terms”¹⁵, the meaning. But the things are not as easy as they seem, because in myths, Roland Barthes finds two semiological systems: *the language-object* (on the basis of which the myth builds its own system) which consists of the actual language (or other modes of representation assimilated to the language) and *metalanguage* or the myth itself (a second language in which we speak about the actual language).

These are only three theories in the field of signs, among the most well-known, theories that have changed the way we look at and interpret things. They focused on all human activities, so that, at present, the field of semiotics has come to have countless subfields.

Human Rights Semiotics

As we have already seen, the human universe is a semiological one; each word, image, oral or written expression, hieroglyph, video etc. can be a sign. We are born and we live in a world full of meanings. That is why every domain from the human universe can be analyzed from a semiotic stand. The legislative field specifically that of human rights, is no exception to this, even if the attempts to understand the specific discourse in this field from a semiotic perspective are relatively recent.

The very expression “human rights” gives rise to discussions related to the question of what it means to have rights, given that, in the main constitutions or documents in which they appeared, they are declared to be universal¹⁶ (so all citizens benefit from them from birth, without exception) - something stated without being questioned and without needing a demonstration, just like an axiom. Even now, state constitutions have clau-

15 *Ibidem*, p. 111.

16 See the Declaration of Independence from 1776 and The Declaration of Rights of Men and Citizen from 1789

ses that refer to the universality of human rights.¹⁷ The fact that all people have human rights is a “self-evident truth” in our society. In reality, different political regimes or groups throughout history have violated other people’s human rights. This suggests that human rights are not universally recognized¹⁸. So we are facing a paradox. Allan Hillani tries to explain how this paradox is possible from a semiotical approach, using in his paper the semiotic rectangle of Greimasian. The graphic illustrates the oppositional structure of a system of signification, also presenting the relations between the contrary and contradictory terms, revealing a complex of meaning possibilities (and also, hidden signifiers implied in this system). The result of his exercise consists in the fact that the political action of human beings is implied within meaning of the expression “having rights”, through the resulting semantic network¹⁹. As the author concludes, Greimasian graphic shows “how the system operates, and how law, politics, and human rights are intrinsically connected in the language of rights”. In the expression “human rights” are included two elements: articulating human rights and being human (not citizen). On the other hand, the process of litigation is also formed by two terms: articulating being citizen and claiming rights (not having rights), that are inscribed in the legal order, simply as “legal demand for recognition of citizen’s rights”. In the graphic the opposition is represented by having rights and being a citizen and the complex term which articulates this opposition is the law. The law attributes the legal situation of the citizen and the rights he benefits from/to which he is entitled. The three parts - human rights, citizen and law - are caught in the discourse regarding the universality of human rights and their violation (which generates litigating processes and the constitutions/laws defining citizenship and granting rights). In this model politics represents a neutral term, which results from the process of claiming rights (not having them) and being human (not being a citizen). The resulting meaning gives sense to both: “being human as result of the activity of claiming; claiming as the inevitable consequence of being human”. The politics (neutral term) stren-

17 For example, article 15 of the Romanian Constitution refers to the universality of rights enjoyed by its citizens, *Constituția României, Camera Deputaților*, online: https://www.cdep.ro/pls/dic/site2015.page?den=act2_1&par1=2#t2c1s0sba15, accessed in May 12, 2023.

18 Hunt, Lynn *apud* Hillani, H. Allan, “The ideology of human rights : on the semiotics of having rights and the politics of being human”, in *Direito, Estado e Sociedade*, No.57, June/September 2020, Editora Pontificia Universidade Catolica do Rio de Janeiro, pp. 11-12.

19 Hillani, H. Allan, *op. cit.*, pp. 26-27.

strengthens the meaning of the two parts of the graphic: political action has as its content the human rights and as its form the litigation. The law is positioned in the Greimasian representation of human rights in contradiction with the politics, but it becomes the object of political action.

Human rights are also ideological and ideology has the power to structure reality in a way that masks its contingency (which in Hillani's thesis is compared to a trauma). In the case of human rights' ideology, politics represents the "traumatic" fact (the contingency of human rights), "as it cannot be fully included in the system, but, at the same time, is its motor function"²⁰. The equality that human rights talk about does not have the role of hiding reality, but is a way of illustrating how people are or appear. The equality of people is part of their common experience and we should not insist upon the difference between the equality as it emerges from the law/constitution and the inequality that may appear in reality. As human rights are ideological, they frame political action, both in the practical field and in the conceptual, theoretical one. But the political action can only appear due to this framing. Therefore, the things that human rights postulate - freedom, equality in rights and dignity - are, even for an instant, a "self-evident" truth.

On the other hand, human rights and obligations being included in legislative acts and constitutions, it is normal for the legal language used in them to also be the object of study of semiotics. Recent research has studied the differences between the specialized language used in the legal field and the everyday language, used by people without training in this field, in relation to their own lived experiences. The researchers came to the conclusion that there is a big discrepancy between the two languages. A representative article on this topic was published by Patricia Williams in the journal *The Michigan Law Review*. Williams talks about three levels of meanings she encountered in legal language:

- a positive interpretation in which the literal meaning of the word is given great authority;
- "a legal realist interpretation, as well as mainstream feminist and civil rights mode of interpretation (squeezing room into meaning for 'me too')"²¹;

20 *Ibidem*, p. 29.

21 Williams, Patricia, "The Obliging Shell: An Informal Essay on Formal Equal Opportunity", in *The Michigan Law Review*, Vol. 87:2128, August 1989, Michigan Law School - University of Michigan, p. 2132.

- an interpretive discourse based on the idea of limits of meaning, “that gives meaning by knowing its bounds”²² (on the form of not knowing how to define an object, but knowing what the object it is not) – by eliminating what the object is not - it permits a bigger range of meanings. The author also states that although she named this “a ‘nihilistic’ critical interpretive stance”, actually it is not nihilism, but a “challenge to contextualize, by empowering community standards and the democratization of interpretation”²³.

In all three levels of meaning, not only for the legal language, but also for the common, ordinary language used by non-specialists in law, there is always an evaluation on how we can interpret and understand someone’s words, using as a reference a scale of meanings from which we have to choose a certain level.

When the law talks about equality and racism is doing so in a formal way, which does not take into account the differences of opinion in society regarding such matters. In reality, in this times dominated by liberal speech (which Williams calls “this era of double-speak-no-evil”) racist rhetoric takes on new forms of expression under the degrading definition of ‘not being comfortable’. Black people are not employed in large numbers or are not promoted, on the grounds that they would not be comfortable in certain posts/positions, being judged as „to weak” or „to strong”. In fact, the motivation behind these explanations is either racism or the existing perception in society that introducing black people into a setup (for example a job in a certain field) would make it “will make it ugly (‘unaesthetic’), imbalanced (‘nonuniform’) and sloppy (‘imprecise’)”.²⁴ Despite the fact that the law talks about equality between people using neutral, empty terms, because, although the rules aka the law does not take into account the color of people’s skin when it talks about the opportunity of equality, in society people are not color-blind and will continue to act unjustly under the cover of the rhetoric of the existing ideology that flows from the laws. So, there are two distinct languages: one that is intended to be neutral, specific to the legal field, with the claim of establishing which rights are inviolable and a second language, based on the first one, but which leads to opposite results

22 *Ibidem.*

23 *Ibidem.*

24 *Ibidem*, pp. 2138-2143.

than the ones required by law, language which hides behind the meanings of the formal language, changing them. This is the description of the phenomenon highlighted by Noam Chomsky regarding political language in which a word is used with a secondary meaning, opposed to the basic one.²⁵

The author raises the issue of whether, regarding equality, the law can exist and can have the desired results in the conditions where it does not specify the existing ideologies in society, which have been preserved throughout time, despite the desire for change in for the better. In other words, "formal juridical equality excludes socially and historically contingent circumstances"²⁶.

The themes addressed by semiotic analysis in the area of human rights are diverse. A series of studies have been carried out on the link between human rights and the law, more precisely how authoritarian the laws can be, the problem of legal language as metalanguage, to what extent the legislators through the language used can include/comprehend the interests of all citizens, considering their different needs, how divergent the legal language in the field can be compared to the spoken languages of non-experts.

Images used by human rights groups or organizations – A Semiotic Analysis

Different symbols, colors or images (representations were also used by different groups, associations or organizations fighting to obtain or protect human rights. Their use was based on the need for recognition, either of the group or organization that appropriated a set of colors or an insignia, or of the message they intended to convey.

The colors used by the suffragettes were not randomly chosen; each color symbolized a different value, highly appreciated in the era and in the territory of the respective country. The Woman's Social and Political Union in The United Kingdom, founded in 1903, was the organization whose main concern consisted in obtaining women's suffrage in England. Their colors, chosen to represent the WSPU - purple, white and green - later

25 Chomsky, Noam apud Farcaș, Ana Daniela, *Coordonate ale filosofiei politice la Noam Chomsky (Coordinates of political philosophy in the works of Noam Chomsky)*, Editura Maestru Tip, 2017, pp. 167-178.

26 Conklin, E. William, "Human Rights, Language and Law: A Survey of Semiotics and Phenomenology", in *Ottawa Law Review*, Vol. 27, Issue 1, published in January 1st, 1995, Faculty of Law, University of Ottawa, p. 172.

formed the WSPU flag. The color purple is often associated with royalty and nobility. In the case of the suffragettes it was also chosen to symbolize “loyalty for the cause and women’s quest for freedom”²⁷. At the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, the European and American cultural spaces were still dominated by Christian values, among which purity of soul had a primary role. The white color had the role of symbolizing purity. Just as the raw green of the leaves in spring signals the revival of nature, bringing hope and confidence in the future, this color also found its place in the flag of the suffragettes. In the United States, the English colors were also adopted, but green was replaced by golden yellow, the bright color of sunflowers²⁸, as a beacon of hope.²⁹

The colors, especially the vivid ones, attract attention; they seem to shout to the viewer. The rainbow, since ancient times, has been associated in the mythology of different peoples as making the connection between the heavenly world, that of the gods and the human world on earth. In China it is the symbol of the harmony of the universe³⁰. Although there are cases in which the appearance of the rainbow is seen as a bad omen, foretelling the arrival of some major unfortunate events, in general it is perceived as announcing happy circumstances. The rainbow was chosen for the first time in 1978 as a symbol for the gay community, by the artist Gilbert Baker, a member of the community. He saw the rainbow as “a natural flag from the sky”. At the beginning the LGBTQIA+ flag displayed eight colors: “hot pink for sex, red for life, orange for healing, yellow for sunlight, green for nature, turquoise for art, indigo for harmony, and violet for spirit”. Later, the same year, the blue color replaced the indigo stripe on the flag and the pink and turquoise stripes were eliminated, the result consisting in the form of the flag that has been preserved until now.³¹ (Gonzalez)

27 Hall, Stephanie, “Symbolism in the Women’s Suffrage Movement” in *Library of Congress Blogs*, online: <https://blogs.loc.gov/folklife/2020/08/symbolism-in-the-womens-suffrage-movement/>, published in August 24, 2020, accessed in May 12, 2023.

28 the sunflower was first adopted by the Kansas women in 19th century, being the state’s flower

29 Hall, Stephanie, “Symbolism in the Women’s Suffrage Movement” in *Library of Congress Blogs*, online: <https://blogs.loc.gov/folklife/2020/08/symbolism-in-the-womens-suffrage-movement/>, published in August 24, 2020, accessed in May 12, 2023.

30 Chevalier, Jean; Gheerbrant, Alain, *Dicționar de simboluri. Mituri, vise, obiceiuri, gesture, forme, figuri, culori, numere* (*Dictionary of symbols. Myths, dreams, habits, gestures, shapes, figures, colors, numbers*), Editura Polirom, Iași, 2019, pp. 319-320.

31 Gonzalez, Nora, “How Did the Rainbow Flag Become a Symbol of LGBTQ Pride?”, published in *Encyclopedia Britannica*, 20 June 2017, <https://www.britannica.com/story/>

Currently there are a number of well-known institutions, non-profit organizations, associations or foundations active in the field of human rights defense. Of these, among the most famous are: Unicef – which focuses its efforts on programs regarding the protection, survival and education of children and Amnesty International – the objects of its campaigns and research consisting of abuses of human rights worldwide, in a wide variety of cases, from the rights of indigenous people, to discrimination, to police abuses or in armed conflicts. These two institutions are well known all over the world for the activities they carry out to promote and support human rights in areas where they are violated.

UNICEF (United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund) was created in 1946 in New York and the organization is part of the United Nations. Its activity is centered on supporting the children of the world through humanitarian and development programs. Its motto in the present is "for every child" and it changed over time, the same as the organization's logo. The actual logo is in use since 2016, when the expression "for every child" was added below the logo formed by the acronym for the organization and the image representing a parent lifting up a child. At its foundation UNICEF took the UN symbol as its logo (the image representing the Earth/the world map surrounded by two olive branches – the symbol of peace in the world). According to the *Dictionary of symbols*, the olive tree, in Jewish and Christian traditions, is the symbol of peace: the dove that announces the end of the flood brings Noah an olive branch³².

The first logo designed for the organization as its own visual identity consists in an image, also partially based on the UN logo (the world map with the olive branches) on top of which was added a child drinking from a glass of milk, with the phrase "for all the world's children" in the upper part of the representation. The reason for adding the child drinking from the glass in the logo is due to the aid actions carried out on that period by the organization, whose main activity at the time was to offer or deliver milk to children. So, in addition to the symbol that attests to the wish for peace to reign throughout the world, the child drinking from the glass, is linked to the activity for which the institution was known at the time, which also symbolizes the fact that UNICEF desires or it takes on the role of

how-did-the-rainbow-flag-become-a-symbol-of-lgbt-pride, accessed in May 12, 2023.

32 Chevalier, Jean; Gheerbrant, Alain, *op. cit.*, p. 575.

suppressing the hunger of children all over the world. In the 60s, with the diversification of programs to help children, the need arose to reflect this in the logo as well. As a result, the place of the “child drinking milk” is taken by the design of the “mother/parent lifting the child”, which is not accidental, as the Declaration of the Rights of the Child was adopted in 1959 by UN. Moreover, the explanation for choice of this semiotic sign by the organization can be found right on its website:

“The universal gesture of a mother lifting up a child symbolizes the hope, security and joy that UNICEF’s work gives to parents and their children. This gesture evokes parents’ energy and enthusiasm, which reflects UNICEF’s optimism and the results we seek to deliver for every child.”³³

Between 1975 and 2001 the logo was changed 3 times, with the mention that the design did not differ much from one model to another. The main change was the introduction of the organization’s acronym written in larger, visible letters, and the image of the mother with the child moving from representing the dot on the letter i in „Unicef” to taking the place to the right of the name. Starting with 2001, short messages were inserted at the bottom of the logo to illustrate the institution’s goals in this way as well. We will present them in chronological order:

- in 2001:
“for every child
Health Education Equality Protection
ADVANCE HUMANITY”;
- in 2008:
“unite for children”;
- in 2016:
“for every child”.

As can be seen, the tendency was to shorten the message, which inevitably led to an apparent loss of the meanings found in the logo. At the same time, the change of the message also brings with it the change of meaning. While the first message suggests that UNICEF brings humanity forward, ensuring that every child has access to health, education, equality, protection, i.e. the main rights in the UN Declaration on the Rights of

33 Tomassini, Martina; Yi, Ruthia, “UNICEF: Hystory of a logo”, UNICEF.ORG, online: <https://www.unicef.org/about-unicef/unicef-logo-history>, accessed in May 13, 2023

the Child, the second message centers on the concept of union. It suggests both the fact that for the protection of children everyone must unite to achieve this goal, the message has the role of exhortation (that we all shall have this goal), but, above all (being part of the visual image of the organization), that all the people who are under the organization's umbrella are united for the common purpose of protecting children.

Fig. 1

UNICEF logo in 1946

UNICEF logo in 1953

UNICEF logo in the 60's

UNICEF logo in 1975

UNICEF logo in 1986

For every child
Health, Education, Equality, Protection
ADVANCE HUMANITY

UNICEF logo in 2001

UNICEF logo from 2001 until present

The idea of unity also appeared in campaigns led by UNICEF in other forms, such as “united for peace” or “united for AIDS”.

At last, the third message conveys that no child will be left behind by UNICEF, it is a message of hope for children and their families who are in unfortunate circumstances and cannot provide for themselves. It also “embodies the organization’s mission to give greatest priority to the most disadvantaged children” and provide them with everything they need. Children’s needs are suggested by the nature of the message, which was designed to be modular: thus, it is considered that the first part of the message consists in the expression “for every child” and the second part, although absent from the logo includes words that show the range of UNICEF’s programs and the hopes that the organization has for them: *dignity, hope, opportunity*. Consequently, the message transforms taking the shape: “*For every child, hope*”. Modularity is a characteristic of our time, inspired by technology and industry. The idea of several component parts forming a whole is not new, it can be found in all historical eras, but nowadays modular design has been adopted in a wide variety of fields. As can be seen, modularity has even influenced the field of visuals or aspects related to advertising design.

At first sight, comparing the way the logo design has changed over time, we can conclude that with the shortening of the message, the number of meanings also decreased. We find, however, that this is not the case: for those in the know, who are aware of the activities or programs in which UNICEF is involved, familiar with the various slogans used in the campaigns, the number of meanings does not differ much. Only the mentioned concepts change. Of course, to those who do not know the organization, not all the meanings contained in the logo are revealed to them. However, they will be able to identify the institution behind it and its field of activity.

Another aspect that should not be lost sight of is the transition from black to blue in 1986, a change explained by the desire to make the logo easier to recognize, but also to keep up with the trends of the time from a visual perspective. The transition from dark blue to cyan in 2001 was also explained from a semiotic point of view: it was hoped that through the new color palette chosen by UNICEF - cyan, yellow, pink and violet (bright, happy colors) - the vibrancy of children could be reflected³⁴.

The times or history (as we find in the semiotic theories) affect the

34 *Ibidem*.

messages, the way they are transmitted to the receivers, the visual appearance of the logos and the meanings that an object can receive. The purpose of the above analysis was to highlight this idea and to also observe that some symbols remain current despite the passage of time, even if the values change over time, and the emphasis shifts in different periods of time on other virtues.

Peter Benensons, the founder of the organization Amnesty International, a British Catholic lawyer, was inspired by the Chinese proverb "Better to light a candle than curse the darkness," when he asked the artist Diana Redhouse to design the emblem of the organization³⁵ (Power, 1981:12, 14). This is how the emblem representing a candle surrounded by barbed wire was born. In a significant gesture, starting with 1961 Amnesty ceremony at the Wren church, St. Martin's-in-the-Fields in London, a candle was lit in a London church, every year with the occasion of Human Rights Day, celebrated in 10th of December. The candles were lit by former prisoners or relatives of former political or religious prisoners, for whose cases the organization campaigned. Moreover, the fight for the release of prisoners imprisoned for political or religious reasons has been the main concern of Amnesty International since its foundation and until today, in accordance with The United Nations Declaration of Human Rights. The organization fights for the fair treatment in prisons and tries by several means to influence the situation of those unjustly imprisoned, sometimes reaching the point of their release.

The candle is a symbol of light, wisdom and illumination, but, as Pope Paul VI specified, "Through its verticality and gentleness, it is the embodiment of innocence and purity". At the same time, the symbolism of the candle also borrows from the symbolism of the flame, or the fire, seen both as a destructive element, but also as a divine element - the sacred fire, which has purifying and regenerative powers. Bachelard gives a special meaning to the candle flame, that of verticality, courage and fragility: "The flame is a brave and fragile vertical. Every breath disturbs the flame, but it recovers. An ascending force restores its brightness".³⁶ (Chevalier, Gheerbrant; 2009:542, 404-407) Considering the organization's concern for the release of unjustly imprisoned prisoners, it is easy to see why barbed wire

35 Power, Jonathan, *Amnesty International The Human Rights Story*, Pergamon Press, Oxford, New York, Toronto, 1981, pp. 12, 14.

36 Chevalier, Jean; Gheerbrant, Alain, *op. cit.*, pp.542, 404-407.

was used in the Amnesty International logo. The barb wire is the sign of imprisonment, if someone wants to escape, it tears the flesh. It represents the risk but also the hopelessness (the darkness) “of people put in jail where they think nobody remembers they are there.”³⁷ The candle in the middle of the barb wire is the hope present in the soul of those unjustly condemned, the flicker of light for those whose rights were wrongfully violated. It also represents Amnesty International’s commitment that it will not give up, it will not forgive but will fight for the good of people unfairly imprisoned, no matter where in the world they are.

On a superficial level the receptor (the viewer) of the message transmitted by the logo sees only the sign, aka the candle and the wire, but after that follows the more complete analyses, second level involvement, according to Barthes’ theory of perception and signs.

In the correlation that exists between the candle and the wire as real objects and the desired message transmitted through their representations, the receptor must take into account both, the proverb from which the founder of the organization started, and the myths existing in the universal culture related to the representations used. The proverb “Better to light a candle than curse the darkness” it is a call to action: better to do something or to confront a problem than complain. Even if the darkness (the problem) is vast and seems endless and invincible, a small candle (trying to do something about it) is still a step in the right direction. Even if the circumstances seem unfavorable, hopeless, beyond our power to face them, it is worth trying - it is a better way than bemoaning them. We can accomplish more through small steps, than doing nothing.

In this particular case, a double analysis must be carried out: that of the text of the proverb – what message it conveys and that of the symbolism of the objects represented in the logo. The two complement each other.

However, part of the message may be lost: for those who do not know the history of the organization and how its logo was created, the first part of the message is not available. In their presumptions they will appeal to the knowledge coming from the culture in which they lived and developed to explain the reason for Amnesty in choosing its emblem.

37 Airey, David, “Amnesty International” in *Logo Design Love*, online: <https://www.logodesignlove.com/amnesty-international-logo-design>, 15 June 2008, accessed in May 13, 2023.

The logo was renewed in 2000, keeping most of the old design, being only brought to modern standards of beauty and sometimes getting the yellow background color. As a result, we must not lose sight of the significance of the color yellow, an intense, warm color, a symbol of light³⁸, in relation to the flame and fire of the candle.

Fig. 2

Amnesty International logo
designed by Diana Redhouse

Fig. 3

The new logo designed by Simon
Endres in 2000

Logos are images sometimes accompanied by text and colors, so the semiotic analysis of a logo is done according to the model of the semiotic analysis of an image, and where appropriate, the written message can be analyzed as a text; also the colors play their role in correlation with the image. As Martine Joly observes, in a visual message can exist three (sometimes more) type of messages: a linguistic message, an iconic message and a plastic message. By analyzing each individual message, but also the interaction between them, “the global implicit message is obtained”.³⁹ Plastic symbols are made up of colors, texture, composition, shape. According to Joly, the differentiation between iconic and plastic signs was made during the 80s, when it was demonstrated that even plastic signs make up a whole from a

38 Chevalier, Jean; Gheerbrant, Alain, *Dicționar de simboluri. Mituri, vise, obiceiuri, gesture, forme, figuri, culori, numere* (Dictionary of symbols. Myths, dreams, habits, gestures, shapes, figures, colors, numbers), Iași, Editura Polirom, 2019, p. 419.

39 Joly, Martine, *Introducere în analiza imaginii*, București, Editura All, 1998, p. 72.

whole part, not being just a matter of expression of iconic signs, the plastic options, contributing to the meaning of the visual message (in this case to the meaning of the analyzed logos)⁴⁰.

Conclusion

We live in a universe full of meanings and we are assaulted by information from everywhere. In order to understand the world and order it, we give meaning to our lives. We do this by transforming the information we receive through various ways into meanings that will get us out of the existential chaos. Therefore, the field of semiotics is indispensable for our evolution. Understanding how we attribute meaning to the objects that surround us or that make up our inner world helps us understand ourselves better and build a greater world for everybody.

Following the principle of the general good through which we aim to achieve a world where everyone enjoys equality and the same privileges we drafted laws with the aim of improving our society in a virtuous, fair one. Constitutions ensure the respect of rights and obligations for all citizens, regardless of race, religion, nationality, age, sexual orientation. The existing values in society influence people's perception of the rights they should benefit from. National values are reflected in the legislation of the states. Between values and legal texts there is the same connection that can be found in semiotics between a signified and a signifier, i.e. the connection between the object (in this case a word) and the concept it represents. Linguists, philosophers, but also theorists from various fields have dedicated themselves to semiotic analysis in various branches of human activity, including that concerning human rights. In this field, as in others, the nature of the objects to be loaded with meanings is different. In this work we have chosen to talk about the relationship between the terms used in the legal language concerning human rights and to do a semiotic analysis of some logos belonging to organizations that activate in this specific field.

Analysis of the terms regarding human rights led to the establishment of the relationship between them. The term 'human rights' is formed from the connection between 'having rights' and 'being human'. In the opposite site of 'human rights' there is the term 'litigation' which is the

40 *Ibidem*, pp. 72-73.

result of the relationship between the terms 'citizen' and 'claiming rights'. In the graph, two terms are revealed to us, which are in a relationship of contradiction with each other: a complex term – 'law' and a neutral term 'politics'. The relationship between terms reflects the way in which these concepts work in reality.

The studies that had as a starting point the legal language of human rights demonstrated that it differs radically from the language used in current speech. It can be said that we are talking about two different languages, one specific to laws, which tries to be neutral, impartial, and another, which manages to include new meanings of words based on the first one. The existence of the second language makes it possible to violate the constitution due to the change in the meaning of some words that end up being mentioned as reasons for discrimination. Discriminatory behavior is proliferating in society under terms such as *equality*, *individual freedom* or even *human rights*.⁴¹ The language of laws differs from the language of society on this topic. The connotations are different which leads to the questioning in the ability of the laws to be successfully applied in society.

The second analysis reflects the way in which a semiotic analysis can be done, this time based not on words or language, but on images as representations of real objects and values in society. Each image carries a symbolic load, a meaning, which was chosen from a multitude of possibilities, depending on several considerations such as historical period/time, the values elevated to the rank of virtues worthy to be followed in society, the way in which the perceptions regarding the artistic vision have changed in different eras etc.

Both analyzes proved that some meanings escape the attention of the receptor who is not specialized or does not know certain codes necessary to decipher the message. Also, certain meanings are easy to perceive at first glance due to the fact that there is a consensus, a general understanding of the signified concept. When the consensus is missing, a signifier can have several different signified (meanings). This implies a higher effort for decoding the message.

41 Ioan-Gheorghe Rotaru, *Om-Demnitare-Libertate*, Cluj-Napoca, Editura Risoprint, 2019, pp.208-215.

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